

second backcross, which probably resulted from the restricted recombination between parental genomes indicated by the low frequency of rod bivalents in the meiosis of the F₁ hybrids. Furthermore, none of the *O. minuta* allozyme (*Sdh1*, *Pgd2*, *Got1*, and *Got3*) was detected in the 24-chromosome plant, indicating lack of introgression of chromosome segment from the donor wild species.

Cited references

- Glazmann JC, delos Reyes BG, Khush GS. 1988. Electrophoretic variation of isozymes in plumules of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) - a key to the identification of 76 alleles at 24 loci. IRRI Res. Pap. Ser. 134.14 p.
- Jena KK, Khush GS. 1984. Embryo rescue of interspecific hybrids and its scope in rice improvement. Rice Genet. Newsl. 1:133-134. ■

Histological observation of callus morphology in rice

J. O. Narciso and K. Hattori, Laboratory of Plant Genetics and Breeding, School of Agricultural Sciences, Nagoya University, Chikusa, Nagoya 464-01, Japan

We evaluated callus morphology, emphasizing cell compositions of rice varieties, through histological observation.

Callus morphology of five indica (IR54, Rc2, Oboshi, 2757, 2764), two japonica (Nipponbare, Tsutsu), and two javanica (Lemonte, Rinatte) varieties was evaluated in two callus induction media. Varieties showing good callus growth 2 and 4 wk after culture were evaluated through histological observations using scanning electron and light microscopes.

Of the varieties tested, IR54, Toboshi, Nipponbare, Tsutsu, and Rinatte exhibited good callus growth. Callus morphology of each subspecies differed from one another. At 2 wk after culture, calli of IR54 and Toboshi were characterized by two callus masses: one was yellow, compact, and smooth-surfaced; the other yellowish with hairy protuberance and green spots. Japonica varieties Nipponbare and Tsutsu and javanica variety Rinatte had almost similar morphology. Calli of both sub-

1. Dehusked grains of a) indica (IR54), japonica (Nipponbare), and javanica (Rinatte) and b) their corresponding callus types.

species were yellowish, compact, and smooth-surfaced. Slight changes in callus morphology were noted 1 mo after culture. Green spots occupied more than 50% of the whole callus mass in IR54. Calli of Nipponbare and Tsutsu became globular and easily disintegrated into small pieces. Callus of Rinatte became friable. Callus types of the three subspecies represented by IR54, Nipponbare, and Rinatte are shown in Figure 1b.

Histological observation through a scanning electron microscope showed that

2. Scanning electron microscopic observation of the cell compositions in the calli of a) IR54, b) Nipponbare, and c) Rinatte. Scale bars = 300 μ.

Genetic analysis of epicuticular structure involving a dripping-wet leaf mutant of rice

K. Nakamura and K. Hattori, Laboratory of Plant Genetics and Breeding, Nagoya University, Chikusa, Nagoya 464-01, Japan

We obtained a dripping-wet leaf mutant among doubled haploid progenies regenerated from rice (*Oryza sativa* L. cv Nipponbare) anther culture. This mutant

each callus type had a distinct cell composition (Fig. 2a-c). Callus of IR54 showed a large, highly compact cell mass with domelike structures. The surface was rough with corrugations (Fig. 2a). Callus of Nipponbare was made up of compact, globular cell masses of about the same size (Fig. 2b). The cell masses were composed of round cells arranged in layers, like a flower. Callus of Rinatte was composed of small, round, compactly arranged cells (Fig. 2c). Light microscopic observation of the resin sections generally showed darkly stained, meristematic cell clusters.

The results of a study using mungbean suggest that cell types in a callus mass relate to embryogenic potential (Narciso and Hattori 1995). This relationship has not been fully studied in rice. Results of this research could provide the basic information needed to establish this relationship.

Cited reference

- Narciso JO, Hattori K. 1995. Different cell compositions in mungbean (*Vigna radiata* (L.) Wilczek) cotyledon calli. Breed. Sci. 45(2):173-177. ■

was derived from callus treated with 20 Gy of gamma rays 2 d after transfer to regeneration medium. Rice leaves, in general, can shed drops of water; however, leaves of the dripping-wet leaf mutant do not because of their highly hydrophilic leaf surface. Many of these mutant types, which are controlled by a single recessive gene, have been obtained in rice. Some of these gene loci have already been identified (Sato et al 1983). Although factors causing high leaf wettability in these mutants are not clear, leaf surface structure